

COMMERCIAL COOKING INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS AND THE BASIC, COMMON AND CORE COMPETENCIES OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

IRENE REYES CAPARAZ¹

DR. DOLORES D. VERSANO²

irene.caparaz@deped.gov.ph¹

dolores.versano@lspu.edu.ph²

ORCID No.0000-0002-3038-4485

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Cookery is perceived today as an instructive methodology that involves at least two cooks working together to develop something that is consumable in the market. Moreover, cooking is depicted as an approach of the coordination of the various aspects making up an individual such as knowledge and skills (Wang, Moore, Roehrig, and Park, 2016). In addition, skills and knowledge in cooking, particularly in commercial cooking involves the utilization of instructional materials that gives a student a background on what should be done inside the kitchen specifically, in commercial cooking, and the skills that should be developed prior to employing the knowledge obtained from instructional materials to the field of practice (Corlu and Capraro, 2019). Hence, the researcher conducted this study to assess the perception of the respondents on the instructional materials in commercial cooking, the level of competency of the respondents in commercial cooking upon using the instructional material, the relationship between the significant relationship between the instructional materials used in commercial cooking and the level of competency of the respondents, and the prediction of instructional materials used in commercial cooking and the level of competency. In accordance to this the findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between the instructional materials used in commercial cooking and the level of competency of the respondents. Furthermore, it was predicted that the four phases in the instructional material significantly contributed to the level of competency of the respondents upon using the instructional materials.

Keywords: Commercial Cooking, Competency, Cookery, Instructional Materials